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Kompleks sonlar tushunchasi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kompleks sonlarning kiritilishi, shartlari ko'rsatilgan. Kompleks sonlar tushunchasi amallar orqali keltilib chiqarilgan bo'lib, kompleks sonlarning algebraik shakli tasvirlangan. Mavhum birlik tushuncha kirilib, kompleks sonning qo'shmasi tushunchasi ochib berilgan. Qarama-qarshi kompleks sonlarning asosiy xossalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kompleks son, haqiqiy son, mavhum birlik, haqiqiy qism, mavhum qism, qo'shma kompleks son, algebraik shakl.

Понятие комплексных чисел

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Аннотация. В этой статье описывается введение и условия комплексных чисел. Понятие комплексных чисел выводится с помощью операций, и описывается алгебраическая форма комплексных чисел. Вводится понятие абстрактной единицы, и объясняется понятие комплексного числа. Представлены основные свойства противоположных комплексных чисел.

Ключевые слова: Комплексное число, действительное число, абстрактная единица, действительная часть, абстрактная часть, комплексное комплексное число, алгебраическая форма.

The concept of complex numbers

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Abstract. This article describes the introduction and conditions of complex numbers. The concept of complex numbers is derived through operations, and the algebraic form of complex numbers is described. The concept of an abstract unit is introduced, and the concept of a complex number is explained. The main properties of the opposite complex numbers are presented.

Keywords: Complex number, real number, abstract unit, real part, abstract part, complex complex number, algebraic form.

Kirish.

Matematikaning rivojlanishi davomida insoniyat ko'plab yangi son turlarini kashf qilgan. Dastlab butun sonlar, keyin esa ratsional va irratsional sonlar tushunchasi paydo bo'lgan. Ammo ayrim algebraik tenglamalarning yechimlari mavjud sonlar to'plamida aniqlanmasligi matematiklarni yangi sonlar turini joriy qilishga olib keldi. Aynan mana shunday ehtiyoj tufayli kompleks sonlar tushunchasi paydo bo'ldi. Kompleks sonlar ustida amallarni ko'rib chiqsak.

Bizga R haqiqiy sonlar to'plami berilgan bo'lsin. $C=R \times R$ to'plamda qo'shish va ko'paytirish amallarini quyidagicha aniqlaymiz:

$$(a, b) + (c, d) = (a + c, b + d)$$

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (ac - bd, bc + ad).$$

Ravshanki, C da aniqlangan qo'shish va ko'paytirish amallari uchun quyidagi shartlar bajariladi:

qo'shishning kommutativligi: $(a, b) + (c, d) = (c, d) + (a, b)$

qo'shishning assotsiativligi:

$$[(a, b) + (c, d)] + (e, f) = (a, b) + [(c, d) + (e, f)]$$

ko'paytirishning kommutativligi: $(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (c, d) \cdot (a, b)$

ko'paytirishning assotsiativligi:

$$[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \cdot (e, f) = (a, b) \cdot [(c, d) \cdot (e, f)]$$

Ushbu qonunning o'rinli ekanligi quyidagi tengliklardan kelib chiqadi:

$$[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \cdot (e, f) = (ac - bd, ad + bc) \cdot (e, f) =$$

$$= (ace - bde - adf - bcf, acf - bdf + ade + bce),$$

$$(a, b) \cdot [(c, d) \cdot (e, f)] = (a, b) \cdot (ce - df, cf + de) =$$

$$= (ace - bde - adf - bcf, acf - bdf + ade + bce).$$

distributivlik qonuni:

$$[(a, b) + (c, d)] \cdot (e, f) = (a, b) \cdot (e, f) + (c, d) \cdot (e, f)$$

Qo'shish va ko'paytirish amallarini bog'lovchi ushbu distributivlik qonuni ham o'rinli bo'lishini tekshirish qiyin emas:

$$[(a, b) + (c, d)] \cdot (e, f) = (a + c, b + d) \cdot (e, f) =$$

$$= (ae + ce - bf - df, af + cf + be + de),$$

$$(a, b) \cdot (e, f) + (c, d) \cdot (e, f) = (ae - bf, af + be) + (ce - df, cf + de) =$$

$$= (ae + ce - bf - df, af + cf + be + de).$$

Ta'kidlash joizki, $(0,0)$ element C to'plamning nol (trivial) elementi, $(1,0)$ element esa birlik elementi bo'ladi, ya'ni:

$$(a, b) + (0,0) = (0,0) + (a, b) = (a, b),$$

$$(a, b) \cdot (1,0) = (1,0) \cdot (a, b) = (a, b).$$

Ma'lumki, ixtiyoriy $(a, b) \in C$ element qarama-qarshi $(-a, -b)$ elementga ega.

Endi biz C to'plamdagi ixtiyoriy noldan farqli (a, b) elementning teskarilanuvchi ekanligini, ya'ni $(a, b) \cdot (x, y) = (1, 0)$ tenglama yechimga ega ekanligini ko'rsatamiz. Ushbu tenglamadan quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz: $(ax - by, ay + bx) = (1, 0)$.

Bu tenglikdan quyidagi ikki noma'lumli tenglamalar sistemasi hosil bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} ax - by = 1, \\ bx + ay = 0. \end{cases}$$

Ma'lumki, bu sistema $(a, b) \neq (0, 0)$ bo'lganda yechimga ega bo'lib,

$$x = \frac{a}{a^2 + b^2}, y = \frac{-b}{a^2 + b^2}$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Demak, (a, b) element uchun teskari element

$$(a, b)^{-1} = \left(\frac{a}{a^2 + b^2}, \frac{-b}{a^2 + b^2} \right)$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

Ta'rif: Qo'shish, ayirish, ko'paytirish va bo'lish amallari aniqlangan C to'plamga kompleks sonlar to'plami, uning elementlari esa **kompleks sonlar** deb ataladi.

Kompleks sonlar to'plamining $(a, 0)$ ko'rinishidagi elementlari to'plamini R_1 orqali belgilaymiz. C to'plamda kiritilgan qo'shish va ko'paytirish amallarini R_1 to'plamda qaraymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} (a, 0) + (c, 0) &= (a + c, 0), \\ (a, 0) \cdot (c, 0) &= (ac, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Ushbu tengliklardan ko'rinadiki, R_1 to'plamdagi qo'shish va ko'paytirish amallari, haqiqiy sonlar to'plamidagi amallar kabi aniqlanadi.

R_1 va R to'plamlar orasida $f((a, 0)) = a$ kabi $f: R_1 \rightarrow R$ akslantirishni qarasaq, ushbu akslantirish biyektiv bo'lib, yuqoridagi tengliklardan uning ko'paytma va yig'indi amallari saqlashi kelib chiqadi. Demak, $(a, 0) = a$ deb olish mumkin.

Kompleks sonlarning algebraik shakli

Agar $(0, 1)$ elementni i orqali belgilasak,

$$i^2 = (0, 1) \cdot (0, 1) = (-1, 0) = -1$$

bo'ladi. Ushbu $i \in C$ elementga **mavhum birlik** deyiladi.

Ixtiyoriy $(a, b) \in C$ uchun

$$(a, b) = (a, 0) + (0, b) = (a, 0) + (b, 0) \cdot (0, 1) = a + bi$$

tenglikni qarasaq, C kompleks sonlar to'plamining ixtiyoriy elementini

$$z = a + bi$$

shaklda yozish mumkinligi kelib chiqadi. Kompleks sonning ushbu ko‘rinishiga uning **algebraik shakli** deyiladi.

Kompleks sonning ushbu ko‘rinishiga uning algebraik shaklidagi a songa kompleks sonning **haqiqiy qismi** deyiladi va $\text{Re}(z)$ orqali belgilanadi. Undagi b soni esa z kompleks sonning **mavhum qismi** deyilib, $\text{Im}(z)$ orqali belgilanadi.

Mavhum qismi nolga teng bo‘lgan kompleks sonlar haqiqiy sonlar bo‘lsa, haqiqiy qismi nol bo‘lgan kompleks sonlar **mavhum kompleks sonlar** deyiladi.

Ushbu $\bar{z} = a - bi$ kompleks soni $z = a + bi$ kompleks soniga **qo‘shma kompleks son** deyiladi. Qo‘shma kompleks sonlar uchun

$$z + \bar{z} = (a + bi) + (a - bi) = 2a$$

$$z \cdot \bar{z} = (a + bi) \cdot (a - bi) = a^2 + b^2$$

tengliklar o‘rinli, ya’ni kompleks sonning o‘z qo‘shmasiga yig‘indisi va ko‘paytmasi haqiqiy son bo‘ladi.

xossa: Kompleks sonlarning qo‘shmasi quyidagi xossalarga ega:

$$a) \overline{z_1 + z_2} = \bar{z}_1 + \bar{z}_2;$$

$$b) \overline{z_1 - z_2} = \bar{z}_1 - \bar{z}_2;$$

$$c) \overline{z_1 \cdot z_2} = \bar{z}_1 \cdot \bar{z}_2;$$

$$d) \overline{\left(\frac{z_1}{z_2}\right)} = \frac{\bar{z}_1}{\bar{z}_2};$$

Kompleks sonning teskarisini topishda uning qo‘shmasidan foydalanish juda qulay hisoblanadi:

$$(a + bi)^{-1} = \frac{1}{a+bi} = \frac{1}{a+bi} \cdot \frac{a-bi}{a-bi} = \frac{a-bi}{a^2+b^2} = \frac{a}{a^2+b^2} - \frac{b}{a^2+b^2}i.$$

Quyidagi tasdiqda $z = a + bi$ kompleks sondan kvadrat ildiz chiqazishning algebraik usulini keltiramiz.

1.1-tasdiq: Bizga $z = a + bi$ kompleks son berilgan bo‘lsin, $u + vi$ uning kvadrat ildizi bo‘lsin, u holda

$$u = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2})}, v = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(-a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2})}.$$

Isbot: Aytaylik, $\sqrt{a + bi} = u + vi$ bo‘lsin. U holda bu tenglikning ikkala tomonini kvadratga ko‘tarsak,

$$(u + vi)^2 = a + bi$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bundan

$$\begin{cases} u^2 - v^2 = a \\ 2uv = b \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

tenglamalar sistemasi kelib chiqadi. Bu sistemadagi tenglamalar har birining ikkala tomonini kvadratga ko‘tarib, so‘ngra ularni qo‘shsak, quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$(u^2 - v^2)^2 + 4u^2v^2 = (u^2 + v^2)^2 = a^2 + b^2.$$

So'nggi tenglikdan $u^2 + v^2 = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$ (ildiz musbat ishorali, chunki tenglikning chap tomoni musbat sonidir). Bu tenglikdan va tenglamalar sistemasining birinchi tenglamasidan quyidagilarni hosil qilamiz:

$$u^2 = \frac{1}{2}(a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}), v^2 = \frac{1}{2}(-a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}).$$

Kvadrat ildiz chiqarib,

$$u = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2})}, v = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(-a + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2})}$$

tengliklarni hosil qilamiz. (1.1) tenglamalar sistemasining ikkinchi tengligiga ko'ra uv ko'paytmaning ishorasi b ning ishorasi bilan bir xil bo'ladi, ya'ni agar $b > 0$ bo'lsa, u va v lar bir vaqtning o'zida musbat yoki manfiy ishorali, agar $b < 0$ bo'lsa, u va v lar turli ishorali bo'ladi.

Shunday qilib, biz ixtiyoriy kompleks sonning ikkita kvadrat ildizi mavjud bo'lib, ular bir-biridan ishorasi bilan farq qiluvchi sonlar bo'lishini keltirib chiqardik.

1.1-misol: $z = -35 - 12i$ kompleks sonning kvadrat ildizlarini toping.

Yechim: Ushbu misolda $a = -35$, $b = -12$ bo'lganligi uchun

$$\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} = \sqrt{1225 + 144} = \sqrt{1369} = 37.$$

Bundan

$$u^2 = \frac{1}{2}(-35 + 37) = 1, v^2 = \frac{1}{2}(35 + 37) = 36$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Demak, $u = \pm 1$, $v = \pm 6$ hamda $b < 0$ bo'lganligi sababi, u va v lar turli ishorali bo'ladi, shuning uchun

$$\sqrt{-35 - 12i} = \pm(1 - 6i)$$

Xulosa qilib aytganda, kompleks sonlarning algebraik shakli haqida ma'lumotlar keltirildi. Algebraik ko'rinishdagi berilgan kompleks sonlarning qo'shmasi haqida keltirilgan ma'lumotlardan kelib chiqadi, har qanday kompleks son uchun uning qarama-qarshisi mavjud. Kompleks sonlardan kvadrat ildiz chiqarish tushuntirildi, misollar orqali ochib berildi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ayupov Sh.A., Omirov B.A. Xudoyberdiyev A.X., Haydarov F.H. Algebr va sonlar nazariyasi. "Tafakkur bo'stoni", 2019 y. 296 b.
2. Ayupov Sh.A., Omirov B.A. Xudoyberdiyev A.X. Abstrakt algebra. "Fan", 2022 y. 252 b.
3. Nazarov R.N, Toshpo'latov B.T., Do'sumbetov A.D. Algebra va sonlar nazariyasi. "O'qituvchi", 1993 y. 304 b..
4. Xodjiyev D.X., Faynleyb A.S. Algebra "O'zbekiston", 2001 y. 304 b.
5. Axler Sh., Linear Algebra Done Right. 3rd Edition. "Springer", 2015, p. 357.
6. Artin M. Algebra. 2nd Edition, "Pearson Education", 2018, p. 560.
7. Connell E.H. Elements of Abstract and Linear Algebra. "Simon Foundation". 2004, p. 146.
8. Fuzhen Zhang. Linear Algebra. The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2009, p. 266.
9. Hefferon J. Linear Algebra. Vermont USA, 2020, p. 525.

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